

**INDONESIAN BILDUNGSROMAN
IN PRAMOEDYA ANANTA TOER'S THE BURU QUARTET**

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A THESIS

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And accepted on the recommendation of

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ABSTRACT

INDONESIAN BILDUNGSROMAN IN PRAMOEDYA ANANTA TOER'S THE BURU QUARTET

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This thesis discusses the problem of why Indonesian nationalism turns to be as oppressive as the Dutch colonialism it replaced. Indonesia, a postcolonial state that declared its independence in the aftermath of World War II, is, following Benedict Anderson, an imagined community born out of the futuristic imagination or desire to create a just, democratic society. In answering that problem, this thesis starts from the hypothesis that that story of Indonesian nationalism can actually be viewed as *bildungsroman*. Indonesian nationalism should be seen as the story of maturing and of education. Dynamicity and hybridity are two crucial aspects in understanding Indonesian nationalism as a *bildungsroman*. Unfortunately, both the perspective of seeing Indonesian nationalism as a *bildungsroman* and the two crucial aspects mentioned above have so far been denied by the postcolonial state regimes in Indonesia.

Pramoedya Ananta Toer's Buru Quartet lends us a great insight to rediscover the *bildungsroman* of Indonesia. The Quartet itself is the *bildungsroman* of Minke, an educated and a hybrid, who we can see as the metonymy, in Lacanian sense, for the story

of Indonesia. Finding the dynamicity and hybridity in Minke means rediscovering the dynamic and hybrid nature of Indonesian nationalism.

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DEDICATION

With the risk of being cliché, I wish to dedicate this humble work for all who search for understanding of others. There will be no peace in this world without understanding. Love of others start with understanding.

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I wish to thank Professor Steve Levin, for his support of this research and for his patience and guidance. He has challenged me to do more, to question more, to be more suspicious than what I usually was. Writing this thesis had been a great intellectual exercise for me because of his guidance and challenge. As the writer of this thesis, I, for instance, tend to assume that my readers knew already many, if not all, the things implied. But with the help of Professor Levin, I learn to start assuming the other way around: that my readers might have only very basic knowledge about my subject matter. Such limited basis will not allow a real understanding of my thesis. And as I wrote in the “Dedication” page, Professor Levin’s understanding of me as an “other” and my efforts to understand him as another “other” are what makes this thesis materialized.

I also wish to express my gratitude for the support and guidance from my second reader, Professor Jay Elliot. In the absence of my first reader due to his Sabbatical year, Professor Elliot had worked alongside with me to prepare the way. I would also thank my third reader, Professor Paul Ropp, whose insights (and emailed questions for my oral defense) have sharpened the analysis of this thesis. With both Professor Elliot and Ropp, because of their seniority, I most of the times felt free to regress. This has become the best part of having them as my readers.

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